

INTERACTION OF SULPHUR MONOCHLORIDE WITH THIOCARBAMIDE AND THIOCARBANILIDE

BY R. H. SAHASRABUDHEY

Sulphur monochloride reacts in an inert solvent medium with thiocarbamide and thiocarbanilide forming salts of "formamidine disulphide" and phenylaminobenzthiazole respectively; a trisulphide or a tetrazine is not produced as postulated by Naik. The mechanism of its reaction with thiocarbamides and allied compounds has been discussed.

The interaction of sulphur monochloride with thiocarbamide and thiocarbanilide has been investigated by Naik (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1166); formation of "sulphidodithiocarbamide dihydrochloride", a trisulphide (I) and of "3:6-dithio-1:2:4:5-tetraphenylhexahydro-1:2:4:5-tetrazine" (II) respectively, has been reported,

(I)

(II)

From the reactions of thiocarbamide with certain acid chlorides (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1886, 49, 190; 1887, 51, 378, 666; 1912, 101, 2171) it appears that under the conditions of the experiment thiocarbamide should form "formamidine disulphide" rather than the above trisulphide. Thus:

Formamidine disulphide dihydrochloride.

The tetrazine constitution (II) for the product from thiocarbanilide has been proposed (Naik, *loc. cit.*) by analogy with the compounds of Hector (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1892, ii 44, 492; 45, 200; *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1176; 1890, 23, 357) and Dost (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1014). The constitution of Hector's compounds cannot, however, be regarded as finally settled (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 32) and contrary to the postulates of Dost it has been shown (Sahasrabudhey and Krall, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 17) that sulphur monochloride reacts with NN-methylphenylthiocarbamide in chloroform medium forming 1-amino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole and not a cyclic disulphide or a hydrazodithiocarbamide. In the case of thiocarbanilide also, the reaction is therefore expected to take an analogous course:

As will be evident from the experimental part, both these expectations have been realised.

Attempts at the oxidation of thiocarbamides with sulphur monochloride in aqueous, acid or dilute alcoholic media were not successful.

Mechanism of the Reaction.—The interactions of S_2Cl_2 with amides, thioamides, thiocarbamides and thiols appear to belong mainly to two groups: (i) where the sulphur atom is directly involved and (ii) where it is the amino group that reacts. In the investigations of Chakravarty (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 964; *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1930, 13 A, 73, 85) and S. Ishikawa (*Sci. Papers Inst. Phys. Chem. Res., Tokyo*, 1925, 2, 299; 1925, 3, 147; 1927-1928, 7, 237) the first mechanism appears to be operative, while studies by Naik (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1166) reveal the occurrence of the second mechanism.

A review of the work of these authors and other pertinent literature shows that the above two groups of reactions can be subdivided into two further categories: (A) where S_2Cl_2 gets condensed, and (B) where it acts as a mere oxidising agent with the elimination of sulphur and HCl. The reactions of thioamides and thiocarbamides belong to group (i) and (B) category (*Sci. Rep. Tokyo Bunrika, Daigaku, Sec. A*, 1934-1935, 2, 17; *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 699, 703; Ray and Das, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 323).

In view of the above considerations, the controversy about the exhibition of tautomerism by thiocarbamides and the work of Hunter (this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 147; 1932, 9, 435, 357, 545, *et seq.*), Dixon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 122, 912; 1908, 93, 18; 1920, 117, 80, 720; 1924, 243), Zincke (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 837; 1909, 42, 2721, 3362, 2275, 2282), Fromm (*Annalen*, 1910, 374, 90; 1915, 394, 284), Hugershoff (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3130, 3136; 1903, 36, 3121) and others, it appears that the primary reaction of a thiocarbamide with S_2Cl_2 should result in an initial anchoring of the acid chloride molecule on the sulphur atom of these compounds. Such a union is necessarily unstable, and the halogen eventually migrates on to one of the amino nitrogens forming a N-halide which in the case of aromatic thiocarbamides most probably undergoes a rearrangement analogous to the intramolecular type of chloramine transformation or/and causes excitation followed by elimination of the nuclear *o*-hydrogen and finally ring-closure giving a benzthiazole.

McClelland and Warren (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1095) believe that the oxidation of thioamides and thioanilides to thiazoles takes place through the intermediate formation of disulphides; this view, however, does not find support from a study of the oxidation of aromatic thiocarbamides (Sahasrabudhey and Krall, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 37).

EXPERIMENTAL

Action of Sulphur Monochloride on Thiocarbamide in absolute Alcohol and Chloroform.—The reaction was carried out as described by Naik and also with varying quantities of reactants. In all cases, a hard yellow mass, identical in its behaviour with the previously described product (Naik, *loc. cit.*, p. 1169) was obtained. But, it contained sulphur in varying proportions and only a fraction of which could be removed by repeated extraction with carbon disulphide. On treatment with water it deposited a further

quantity of sulphur. The aqueous extract was strongly acidic and corresponded fully to the description given by Naik.

It is not possible to crystallise the yellow mass from any of the more common solvents and since it contains varying proportions of sulphur, it cannot be considered as a definite compound. Sulphur is most probably held in a sort of pseudo solution by "formamidine disulphide" which is the principal product of the reaction (*vide infra*).

The identity of the product in the aqueous extract with formamidine disulphide has been proved by the following facts: (i) It liberated iodine from aqueous potassium iodide solutions. (ii) On treatment with dilute nitric and picric acids a nitrate (m.p. 138° d.) and picrate (m.p. 154° d.) were obtained. Identity of these with the nitrate and picrate of formamidine disulphide (Werner, *loc. cit.*) was established by undepressed mixed melting points taken with genuine samples. (iii) The aqueous extract on boiling or treatment with alkali deposited sulphur, and on evaporation crystals of thiourea were obtained along with a syrupy viscous residue which proved to be cyanamide.

The reaction of S_2Cl_2 on thiocarbamide was also carried out in chloroform medium with identical results.

Action of Sulphur Monochloride on Thiocarbanilide in Benzene and Chloroform.—

The reaction was carried out according to Naik's procedure. Prismatic crystals melting at 159° (Naik gives m.p. 160°) were obtained in a small quantity. On treatment with acetic anhydride they gave an acetyl derivative, m.p. $162-63^{\circ}$.

The identity of these compounds with phenylaminobenzthiazole, prepared by the action of bromine on thiocarbanilide according to Hegershoff's procedure and its acetyl derivative respectively, was established by undepressed mixed melting points.

As the yield of the product was very poor, in view of the brisk reaction between S_2Cl_2 and thiocarbanilide solution, it appeared that heating for a long time (3 hours in the above experiment) might have led to secondary changes. Following procedure was found satisfactory:

Thiocarbanilide (4 g.) was taken in about 50 c.c. of the solvent (benzene or chloroform) and 2 c.c. of S_2Cl_2 in 10 c.c. of the same solvent were gradually added. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath under a reflux condenser for about 20-30 minutes when the initially brisk evolution of HCl slackened. On evaporation of the solvent, a yellow, sticky residue was left behind, which on extraction with 50 c.c. of rectified spirit gave 3.6 g. of a crude crystalline product. It was crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 159° , and gave an acetyl derivative, m. p. $162-63^{\circ}$.

The author wishes to express his thanks to Prof. H. Krall for his interest and to Principal S. S. Joshi and Prof. P. S. Varma for the facilities.